

Structural engineered wood for construction

Engineered wood products (EWP) are contemporary composite materials, which exhibit high physical and mechanical properties. They can be used as columns, beams, walls, roofs, ceilings and other building components. EWP are made from a variety of wood pieces in various shapes that are either bonded by a high performing adhesive or are mechanically fastened. Many different types are currently produced, including plywood (glued sheets of laminated veneers with alternating grain direction layers), cross-laminated timber (CLT, made of cross-stacked timber planks bonded together under high pressure), glued laminated timber (glulam, composed of several timber layers glued together with high-performance adhesives), laminated veneer lumber (LVL, glued thin wood veneers) and oriented strand boards (OSB, oriented rectangular-shaped strands of wood).

Regional coverage and transferability

Manufacturing companies of EPW have been identified across Europe. The products are structurally sound and suitable replacements for other construction materials. EWPs are even suitable for multi-storey buildings in any region as they can provide high fire resistance and seismic safety. As such, they are increasingly used in areas with strong winds and high seismic safety demands.

Image: Gabberó

Why is it a good practice?

- ▶ They are designed and manufactured to maximize the inherent strength and stiffness characteristics of wood, making more efficient use of wood, as they are made from smaller pieces of wood
- ▶ They are industrialized innovative products and thus can be manufactured as ready-to-use elements or systems and then be delivered to construction sites reducing on-site assembly time.
- ▶ They enable the load-bearing capacity of timber panel elements in both directions, increases load-bearing capacity and limits splitting while ensuring the dimensional stability of panels.
- ▶ They improve awareness for wood as a suitable alternative for high-demand architectural designs and just-in-time production of buildings.
- ▶ Reuse of engineered wood is possible, but regulations for their usage must be developed.